

Deliverable D6.2

Data inventory to support the overall sustainability and impact assessment

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PRO	Technical/economic progress report (internal work package reports indicating work status)	
DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

PROJECT BENEFICIARIES:

JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
IPMA	Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera, Portugal
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna, Italy
Eurofish	Eurofish International Organization, Denmark
UNIFI	Università degli Studi di Firenze, Italy
UMF	University of Medicine and Pharmacy, "Iuliu Hațieganu" Cluj-Napoca, Romania
DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Denmark
BTU	Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany
NORCE	Norwegian Research Centre, Norway
EuroFIR	European Food Information Resources, Belgium
UNIPD	University of Padova, Italy
ABT	AquaBio Tech, Malta
REDINN	RETE EUROPEA DELL'INNOVAZIONE, Italy
BELIT	Preduzece za informacione tehnologije i elektronsko trgovanje BELIT DOO, Serbia
MICRUX	MICRUX FLUIDIC SL, Spain
JdIC	DE LA CUEVA GONZALEZ COTERA JAVIER, Spain
CETGA	Centro Tecnológico del Cluster de la Acuicultura, Spain
DigitalSmart	DigitalSmart DOO, Monte Negro
Bugenvila	BUGENVILA INVESTICIJE DOO, Croatia
OXY	Oxyguard, Denmark

ASSOCIATED PARTNER ORGANISATIONS:

WRG	WRG Europe Ltd, United Kingdom
EAS	EU Aquaculture Society, Belgium

CLLs	Co-creation Living Labs
E-LCC	Economic Life Cycle Coasting
E-LCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
FCR	Food Conversion Ratio
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCT	Life-Cycle Thinking
RAS	Recirculating Aquaculture Systems
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first WP6 and aims to establish a data inventory supporting the FishEUTrust project's sustainability and impact assessment by detailing the collection and treatment of farm and supply chain data. This involves gathering information on production, feed, infrastructure, processing, distribution, and labor using standardized spreadsheets. The data is then used to determine intermediary flows, create correspondence tables for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) processes, and calculate environmental impacts. An example assessment of sea bream production highlights the importance of renewable energy for competitive Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS).

The comprehensive data collection and analysis methodology in WP6 will support robust sustainability and impact assessments within the FishEUTrust project, providing insights into optimizing aquaculture production for environmental and socio-economic benefits.

1. Introduction

The FishEUTrust project aims to enhance transparency and sustainability in the seafood supply chain. Our primary focus is on fostering the growth of high-quality, pan-European farmed seafood and our approach addresses dietary considerations, promoting consumer health, and influencing consumer behaviors toward sustainable aquaculture and the blue economy.

The innovation at the heart of FishEUTrust is the integration of different stakeholders, actors and consumer sectors in a common platform. This platform will link technology providers with supply chain stakeholders engaged in socio-economic analysis to provide optimised business models and regulatory/policy actors to co-develop tools, systems and protocols across the seafood value chain that are intended to increase consumer awareness, engagement, and confidence.

Three WPs will build on the project results and represent its interaction with external parties to increase transparency and traceability in fish supply chain and consumer trust and uptake of seafood. The overall aim of WP6 is to quantify the health, environmental, economic and social impacts of FishEUTrust systems and will provide support for regulation and policy framework.

Figure 1. The three pillars of the Life-Cycle Thinking with the integrated health assessment in SLCA

The integrated assessment to improve FishEUTrust products environmental, economic and social sustainability, enhance their resilience and ensure their healthiness will be used. A Life-Cycle Thinking (LCT) approach will be adopted (Figure 1). This approach will be based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA), Economic Life Cycle Costing (ELCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), allowing the interaction within stakeholders and providing quantitative and qualitative results for both LCT practitioners and non-practitioners. The methodological framework and the Social Life Cycle Assessment will be integrated with a health assessment to evaluate health and well-being. The nutritional value will be modelled and translated into a net health impact using DALYs as a standard unitary

measure.

WP6 consists of three tasks which were developed to achieve this objective. In T6.1 data collection procedures for the inventory phase will be developed. Data will be gathered for all relevant inputs and outputs for each life cycle stage, activity types, processes and elementary flows. T6.2 will quantify the health, environmental, economic and social impacts of FishEUTrust systems (CLLs in aquafarms, innovative technologies and seafood products) by performing an integrated sustainability assessment on the entire life cycle of these systems. Health, environmental, economic and social implications will be explored, and hot spots and key risks regarding the three pillars of sustainability will be identified and delivered to WP1-WP5, as basis for improvements. These data will support an integrated sustainability assessment of FishEUTrust by exploring environmental, economic, social and public health impacts and provide a roadmap for the improvement and sustainable growth of FishEUTrust products (T6.3). After verification, the upscaling phase will allow stakeholders at the local, national, and international levels to conceptualise and exploit the results. Further, the results will comply with the current relevant legal framework and the future EU framework for food sustainability labelling.

This report presents the activities involved in carrying out T6.1.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable D6.2: *Data inventory to support the overall sustainability and impact assessment* is the first deliverable in WP6 and aims to provide a framework for data collection. It describes the data collection sheet and data treatment to determine an inventory that supports the overall FishEUTrust sustainability and impact assessment. This deliverable also corresponds to project Milestone 12 (MS12), which ensures that common scenarios and data collection assessments are defined.

1.2 Relation to other activities in the project

Table 1 illustrates the primary relationships of this deliverable with other activities within the work packages (WPs) of the FishEUTrust project. Specifically, WP6 will gather data from WP1 through WP5, and the outcomes of WP6 will serve as the input for WP7 in developing seafood passports.

Table 1: Relation to other activities in the project

WP	Contributions
WP1	The CLLs plays an active role in obtaining relevant data from fish farms and supply chain. This will enable comparisons between open and closed environments, as well as organic aquaculture, by automating the linkage between aquaculture techniques, feed regimes, and their associated impacts, alongside the evaluation of new RAS technology.
WP2	Input related to social life cycle assessment.
WP3	Input related to economic LCC. Economic impacts in terms of value chain costs and value-added distribution will be considered.
WP4	Input related to environmental aspect and traceability, quality and safety of seafood products. We will evaluate the microbiome and feed quality, focusing on changes in omega-3 and other fatty acid contents, by systematically comparing different modes of aquaculture production with wild fish. The impact on human health will be estimated based on available data, considering 15 dietary risk factors that contribute to 50 diseases identified in the global burden of disease study.
WP5	Input related to safety. Smart control systems for detecting biological and chemical contaminants such as pathogens, antibiotics, and toxins.

1.3 Deviation from the plan

No major deviations are reported. However, to obtain relevant data for assessment more communication and coordination are needed. In the next period face-to-face meeting with different CLLs and stakeholders are planned.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

The content of this deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 describes the data collection approach that involves systematically gathering information on specific variables to measure and evaluate outcomes.
- Section 3 describes determination of intermediary flow by linking the amount of specific materials to certain production steps and integrate the material's lifespan.
- Section 4 presents the identification and matching to inventory process.
- Section 5 determines the environmental impact assessment.

The last chapter is related to Conclusions.

2. Data collection approach

Data collection involves systematically gathering information on specific variables to measure and evaluate outcomes. It is a crucial process across various disciplines, where accurate data collection is emphasized to ensure the reliability and validity of the results.

Figure 1 outlines the main sections of this report and the four main steps for data collection and preliminary data analysis toward establishing this inventory:

1. We first collect the **aquaculture farm and supply chain data** and present the data collection spreadsheet to be filled for each farm and supply chain.
2. We determine the inventory intermediary flow, accounting for infrastructure lifespan and overall farm production.
3. We create correspondence tables to identify and match the Life Cycle Inventory processes existing in most common life cycle database that correspond to the intermediary flows from 2.
4. We demonstrate the calculation of the life cycle inventory and impact assessment via an illustrative example of sea bream from cradle-to-grave, assessing the production of 100 tonnes of sea bream based on data collected data from the literature.

Figure 2. Flow of the data collection and analysis steps

2.1 Farm Data Collection

The data collection excel file (File: DataSpreadsheet.xlsx - Appendix A1) contains five different sheets for partners to fill in the required data for the life cycle assessment. Combining these sheets allows for a thorough farm evaluation from the beginning of the farming process, starting with

juvenile stages through the supply chain until the fish arrives at the supermarket. Each sheet has highlighted sections in red that indicate high priority and must be collected from the farms. The farm data collection spreadsheet is organized according to the five main stages of the aquaculture production (Figure 2). In the **production** sheet, we define the main inputs and outputs in terms of fish, juveniles, and adults, as well as the auxiliaries used for production and data on water quality. The required farm infrastructure and the feed used in the production are further detailed and collected in two separate sheets on **infrastructure** and **feeds**, then on the **processing and distribution supply chain**, with additional social and employees risk data in a final collection tab **Labor**.

Figure 3. Flow chart of the sea bream production system

Production

The first sheet, 'Production' (Figure 3), collects general farm information regarding the yearly production, stocking densities, auxiliaries, and water quality. Knowing the number of fish produced from the farm, the electricity used, and how much water is consumed throughout the yearly measurement period is essential. Understanding the production volume from the farm allows us to create an assessment that could be scaled to different production values based on the resources used. We also use this data to understand the efficiency of the farm, for example, how much electricity is needed to produce 100 tonnes of sea bream, which can allow further analysis for system optimizations. To provide further metrics on investments in aquaculture, we also ask farm partners for cost data when it is available. This way, the costs per ton can be analyzed, including the production instead of just the market costs, painting a more detailed picture of sea bream farming in Europe from both environmental and socio-economic points of view.

Information									
Farm name	Natalie's Nautical Seafood								
Description	Sea bream farm using recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) indoors								
Address	Greece								
Contact	Natalie Rizzo natri@dtu.dk								
Number of employees	4								
Turnover	400,000 Euros								
Fish									
Fish outputs & production	Annual quantity kg/year	Stocking density kg/m ³	Growth rate kg/fish/year	Harvest size kg	Duration months				
Adult sea bream	100000	50	0.4	0.5	18				
Fish Inputs	Annual quantity kg/year								
Juvenile sea bream	40000								
Utilities & auxiliaries									
Electricity	Amount kWh/yr	Price Euro/kWh	Cost Euro/yr	Percent Renewables	Notes				
Part 1		0.063							
Part 2		0.063							
Total	2000000	0.063	126000		2.9 to 81.4 kWh/kg fish according to Dworak et al., 2023, selected 20				
Gas/Heat	Units m3/yr	Units Euro/m3	Time Euro/yr	Percent Renewables	Notes				
Total									
Water Use	Amount per day m3/day	Percent change %/day	Amount per year m3/year	Price Euro/m3	Cumulative costs Euro/yr	Fraction discharged to waste water treatment plant (WWTP) %	Fraction released to freshwater %	Fraction released to ocean water %	Notes
New water input - tank seawater	26	0.26	9496.5	0	0				
New water input - tank freshwater	NA		#VALUE!	0.2	#VALUE!				
Freshwater- cleaning/other use	0.5		182.625	0.2	36.525				
Seawater- cleaning/other use	0.5		182.625	0	0				
Total freshwater			182.625		#VALUE!				
Total seawater			9679.125		0				

Figure 4. Data collection tables for fish inputs and outputs, utilities and auxiliaries

This production sheet also offers the option to the farmer to provide data on water quality and medical and chemical usage in case it is available (Figure 4).

Water Quality									
This section is for reporting of water quality metrics for the tank systems and intake/discharge water.	Volume of water lost per year	Temperature °C	pH	Dissolved oxygen mg/L	Ammonia mg/L	Nitrate mg/L	Total suspended solids mg/L	CO2 mg/L	Alkalinity mg/L
Yearly Average Farm	#REF1	20	8	7	0.2	0.3	10	10	150
Yearly Average Intake	9496.5	20	8.2	6	0.01	0.01	20	5	100
Yearly Average Discharge	9496.5	20	8	7	0.2	0.3	11	10	150
Medical and Chemical									
This section is for reporting antibiotics, medicine and chemicals used on the farm.	Amount per year	Price	Cumulative cost	Cost released to WWTP	Cost released to freshwater	Fraction released to ocean water	Notes		
Medicine oxytetracycline	kg/yr 2	Euro/kg 30	Euro/yr 60	%	%	% 0	Dose 50mg/kg		
Chemicals	Amount per year kg/yr	Price Euro/kg	Cumulative costs Euro/yr	Fraction released to WWTP %	Fraction released to freshwater %	Fraction released to ocean water %	Notes		
Peracetic acid	0.5044	5	2.522						
Bleach	3.465	3	10.395						
Sodium thiosulfate	105.21	6	631.26						

Figure 5. Water quality, medical, and chemical data collection tables

Feeds

The second sheet collects data for the feeds used during production and details the amount of feed and the detailed feed composition (Figure 5). Throughout all life cycle assessment data in aquaculture studies, feeds contribute highly to the impact categories because of the diversity and transport involved for the feed ingredients. It is also important across different life stages of the fish since juveniles may have a different food conversion ratio (FCR) than adults. The farm could produce its own juveniles or purchase them from another farm; either way, the juvenile stage is essential in our assessment and will be included regardless of the main farm partner.

Also included in this data collection tab are data regarding the nutritional analysis and quality of the fish for human consumption (Figure 6). These can help set a baseline for health index reports and analyze losses of healthy metrics along the supply chain. This data is not required, but it would be useful in the assessment if the farms could access it. Previous literature values regarding pollutants in sea bream and nutritional analysis of the sea bream filets were also used in the modeled scenario as a health metric.

Feed							
This section lists the amount of each feed used on farm per year, how often feeding occurs, the feeding method and the ingredients in the feed.							
Feed amount							
Feed #	Feed name	Brand	FCR kg feed/ kg fish	Annual quantities kg feed / year	Annual costs Euro/year	Frequenc y times/day	Notes
1	Adult sea bream feed	Skretting	1.5	150000	246981.3392	2	times/day
2	Juvenile feed	Skretting	1.2	48000	96000		
3							
Feed Composition							
Feed #	1	2	3	4	5		
Feed name	Adult sea bream feed	Juvenile sea bream food					
Brand	Skretting	Skretting					
Cost Euro/kg	1.65	2					
Ingredients	Composition in %	Compos ition in %	Composition in %	Composition in %	Composition in %		
corn oil	6.0%	7.0%					
wheat gluten meal	20.0%	15.0%					
soybean meal	8.0%	10.0%					
wheat	23.8%	25.0%					
soybean oil	12.6%	20.0%					
fish oil	6.9%	9.0%					
fish meal	15.0%	7.0%					
rapeseed oil	4.6%	3.0%					
phosphate	1.0%	1.0%					
vitamin mix	0.3%	0.9%					
lecithin	2.0%	2.0%					
yttrium premix	0.1%	0.1%					
Total	100.3%	100.00%					

Figure 6. Feed quantities and composition data collection tables

Fish Nutritional Analysis	Unit	Sea Bream,			
		Raw	Sea Bream, cooked		
Alcohol	g	0.0	0		
Ash	g	1.3	2		
Biotin	ug	1.0	1		
Calcium	mg	41.0	51		
alpha-carotene	ug	0.0	0		
beta-carotene	ug	0.0	0		
Carotenoids	ug	0.0	0		
Carbohydrates	g	0.0	0		
Cholesterol	mg	56.0	48		
beta-cyptoxanthin	ug	0.0	0		
Chloride	mg	109.0	455		
Copper	mg	0.2	0		
Energy	kcal	116.0	119		
Monounsaturated fatty acids	g	1.4	1		
Polyunsaturated fatty acids	g	1.3	1		
Saturated fatty acids	g	1.0	1		
Fats	g	4.5	4		
Trans fatty acids	g	0.0	0		
Iron	mg	0.8	1		
Fiber	g	0.0	0		
Folate	ug	8.0	11		
Iodine	ug	23.0	23		
Potassium	mg	413.0	393		
Magnesium	mg	27.0	37		
Manganese	mg	0.1	0		
Sodium	mg	76.0	296		
Niacin	mg	4.2	4		
Phosphorus	mg	215.0	258		
Pantathenic acid	mg	0.5	1		
Protein	g	19.0	20		
Retinol	ug	16.0	21		
Riboflavin	mg	0.1	0		
Selenium	ug	39.0	39		
Starch	g	0.0	0		
Sugar	g	0.0	0		
Thiamin	mg	0.1	0		
Vitamin A	ug	16.0	21		
Vitamin B12	ug	2.0	2		
Vitamin B6	mg	0.3	0		
Vitamin C	mg	0.0	0		
Vitamin D	ug	5.9	6		
Vitamin E	mg	1.1	1		
Water	g	75.9	73		
Zinc	mg	0.9	1		
% FAPUN3	%	79.1	79		
%FAPUN6	%	20.9	21		
FAPUN3	g	1.0	1		
FAPUN6	g	0.3	0		
EPA 20:5(n-3)	g	0.1	0		
DHA 22:6(n-3)	g	0.6	0		
Fish Quality Characteristics					
Type	Date	sample size	Average	Unit	
Torrymeter	03-Jan-24	500	8.3±0.4	unitless	
Fish Contaminants					
Type	Date	sample Size	Average	Unit	Notes
Microplastics	12-Dec-23	22	0.8±1.1	MP/fish	rect.com/science/article/pii/
PCB	13-Dec-23	27	34	ngg-1/fresh weight	om/science/article/pii/S00
Mercury					

Figure 7. Nutritional and quality data collection tables

Infrastructure

The third sheet collects infrastructure information regarding the production facilities. Any object and/or materials used to produce the 100 tonnes of sea bream should be recorded on this sheet (Figure 7). Data recorded on the items includes their mass, materials, lifespan, and cost. For example, a farm might use a 145 m² tank made of fiberglass and polyurethane coating with a lifespan of 25 years. Using these metrics, we can attribute impacts (carbon footprint, ecosystem health, etc.) of these materials regarding their lifespan and the total tonnes produced within them and look at their role in the environmental analysis. With the collection of costs of these items, we can look at the item's value based on its lifespan and environmental footprint. The cost data might also be used by WP3 to set up the business model.

Infrastructure												
This section comprises of the farming infrastructure i.e. all the components of the tank system, maintenance, and electricity used.												
All data are related to total production as in Production and feed tab												
Equipment (type of pump, tanks, etc.)	Amount	Brand and Model	Material(s)	Weight per Unit kg	Cumulative Weight kg	Size per unit	Cumulative Size	Units	Lifespan yr	Cumulative Cost Euros	Cost/year Euros	Notes
Tank nursery	5		PP/PVC/Zinc coat			20	100	m ³				
Tank transition	2		PP/PVC/Zinc coat			145	290	m ³				
Tank growth	4		PP/PVC/Zinc coat			145	580	m ³				
Total Tanks	11						970	m³	20	€ 155,326	€ 7,766	Grouped price
Drum filter	1	ED-PP-30,	PP	400	400	250	250	m ³ /h	10	€ 5,466	€ 547	https://www.alibaba.com/product
Pump	1	cluded in drum filter							10	€ 0	€ 0	
Protein skimmer	1	EPS-30,FC	PVC/PP				0.9	KW	10	€ 2,278	€ 228	https://www.alibaba.com/product
Biological Filter	1	EM88-60	HDPE, PVC, PP	500	500		2.25 x 2.25	m	30	€ 1,822	€ 61	https://www.alibaba.com/product
UV disinfection	1	Viper 400W SS UV	stainless steel,				0.4	KW	10	€ 3,644	€ 364	https://playitkoi.com/products/aq
UV bulb	1								1	€ 91	€ 91	https://pentairaes.com/water-to-wa
Heat exchanger	1	pentair HX-120W	titanium, SS, PVC			.34 x .64 x 1.34, 1200		m, BTU/h	10	€ 3,644	€ 364	https://www.alibaba.com/product
Degasser (CO2 removal)	1	E-DG-60	PP,			1 x .50 x .50		m	10	€ 1,549	€ 155	https://www.alibaba.com/product
Oxygenation column	1		aluminum, steel, plastic, pvc, wires	230	230	1.25 x 0.7 x 1.70		m	10	€ 2,733	€ 273	https://www.alibaba.com/product
Pipe Schedule 80 PVC (3")	1		PVC			50		m	20	€ 1,640	€ 82	
oxygen/ph/CO2 meters	3	oxyguard	PP/stainless steel/						10	€ 4,100	€ 410	
Feeding tool	0								10	€ 0	€ 0	
Air compressor												
Chilling tub	3	Plastico	molded plastic	35	105	500		m ³	50			

Figure 8. Data collection table for farm infrastructure and equipment

Processing and Supply Chain

After the production and infrastructure data is collected, processing, packaging, and transport information is necessary for the impact assessment. Data from the supply chain starts at the slaughter at the processing facility, where the fish is gutted and then pre-packaged for transport to the packaging facility, where the fish is packaged for supermarkets. After this packaging step, distribution across Europe begins at a larger distribution center and then to local transport. Collecting the kilometers traveled, packaging materials, and time spent at each step are used to evaluate the environmental impact and any health data that can be linked to the time spent in transport (Figure 8).

Slaughter Materials									
Materials needed for slaughter									
Item	Amount per year	Weight per unit kg/year	Cumulative weight	Cost/unit euros	Cumulative cost euros	Materials	Notes		
Ice	100	100	10000 0 0 0	0.1	1000 0 0 0	water, plastic			
Packaging									
This section includes packaging and materials used for the distribution of 1000 tonnes of sea bream and the kilometers traveled.									
Item	Amount unit/year	Unit	Material	Weight per unit kg/unit	Cumulative weight kg/year	Cost/unit euros/unit	Cumulative cost euros/year	Notes	
Plastic wrap	100	rolls of plastic wrap	polystyrene	10.5156	1051.56	9	900	451ef19b1c4a.jpg&sj	
Foam food seafood tray	333333	foam trays	PET foam	0.02	6667	0.018	6000	osable-Black-Foam_1	
Farm to Wholesale									
Transport methods between farm and processor/wholesaler									
Route	Distance km	Type	Weight-distance tkm	Cost/km euros/km	Cumulative cost euros	Notes			
Farm to processor	77	Refrigerated truck	#REF!	1.25	#REF!				
Processor to wholesale	2294	Refrigerated truck	#REF!	1.25	#REF!				
Supply Chain Timeline									
Average time of batch: 4 days									
Time Points	Time of kill	Farm Departure	Arrival at Processor	Departing Processor	Arrival to Distributor	Depart Distributor	Arrival to Wholesale	Total	Units
Date	Jan 3, 2024	Jan 3, 2024	Jan 3, 2024	Jan 4, 2024	Jan 4, 2024	Jan 5, 2024	Jan 5, 2024		
Time	06:00:00	12:00:00	15:00:00	06:00:00	18:00:00	03:00:00	05:00:00		
Duration at Step (hours)		6	3	15	12	9	2		hours
Cumulative hours from kill	0	6	9	24	36	45	47	167	average temperature
Temperature between steps (celcius)		4	5	4	4	3	4	4	
Distance from previous step (km)			30		2248		46		

Figure 9. Packaging and distribution data collection table

Labor

Data collection on labor and workforce includes the number of employees, their duties, and the risk assessment. This data collection assists in evaluating the socio-economic benefits of sea bream aquaculture and can be used in a social LCA framework (Figure 9). It will enable us to assess the social aspects of aquaculture and the risks involved.

Farm Labor										
This section production lists labor involved. Give a percentage of the job that is dedicated to each task										
Positions	Managing %	Maintenance %	Feeding %	Husbandry %	Misc %	Hours per week h/week	Cost €/year	Cost €/year	Gender	Notes
Farm supervisor	90%	5%			5%	40	50,000	50,000	Female	
Aquaculture technician	0%	30%	30%	30%	10%	40	30,000	30,000	Male	
Part time technician		45%	10%	45%		20	15,000	15,000	Other	

Packaging and Processing Labor							
Fish weight processed per year This section production lists labor involved.							
Positions	Number of workers	Hours per workers per day h/worker/week	Cumulative hours h/year	Cost per hour €/h	Cumulative €/year	Gender	Notes
Supervisor	2	40	4160	25		Female	
Packager	4	40	8320	15		Male	
			0				
			0				

Labor - Risk Assessment																	
Positions	Training hours per year	Hours of risk exposure per week	Average satisfaction of the workers (1-5 Likert scale, 1 low, 5 high)	Hired locally	Belonging to disadvantaged category	Risk exposure (see description in the textbox to the right)											
	h/year	h/week		y/n	y/n	Safety		Physical		Chemical		Biological		Ergonomic		Psychosocial	
						If yes, what type of risk?	If yes, then h/week	If yes, what type of risk?	If yes, then h/week	If yes, what type of risk?	If yes, then h/week	If yes, what type of risk?	If yes, then h/week	If yes, what type of risk?	If yes, then h/week	If yes, what type of risk?	If yes, then h/week

Figure 10. Data collection tables for labor positions and risk data

3. Determination of intermediary flows and materials

After the data collection sheet is completed and returned, the data is compiled into tables to create the intermediary flows of the inventory step (Table 2). These tables organize the inputs of each step in the farming process and summarize all the materials used per functional unit (e.g. 100 tons of sea bream produced). Here, we can link the amount of specific materials to certain production steps and integrate the material's lifespan. For example, the amount of polyethylene in the floating rings for the net pen farm is 166,646 kilograms with a 10-year life span. Thus, we divide this amount by the material's lifespan, equaling 16,664.6 kilograms per 100 tons of sea bream produced. For the infrastructure, the lifespan is provided separately for each material and/or component.

Table 2. Intermediary collection of materials from different literature values from previous LCA studies.

Infrastructure				
Offshore	Floating Ring	Net	Mooring	kg/FU
polyethylene	X			16664.60
polystyrene	X			0.02
nylon		X		4121.40
polypropylene		X	X	4298.54
polyethylene			X	0.06
polyurethane			X	0.07
polyvinylchloride			X	0.00
cast iron			X	0.07
steel, chromium			X	801.92
steel, low-alloyed			X	5509.88
concrete			X	0.04
RAS	Tank	Filtration	kg/FU	
Stainless steel	X		778.4	
Fiber glass	X		2688	
clay	X		2196.88	
glass pvc		X	29.68	
heat pump		X	0.08	
sand		X	655.2	
Feed	kg/FU			
Fish meal	40000			
fish oil	18000			
wheat grain	26000			
soybean meal	42000			
wheat gluten meal	30000			
corn oil	22000			
rapeseed oil	10000			
soybean oil	8000			
vitamins	2000			
monocalcium phosphate and methionine	2000			
energy				
electricity (kW)	187896			
Heat (Mj)	851326			
Materials	0			
wooden pallets (pieces)	160			

LDPE film/bags (kg)	1100			
Production				
Electricity	kWh/FU			
Offshore	814			
RAS	2000000			
Offshore Production				
diesel combustion	1400			
petrol combustion	190			
Water	m3/FU			
Ice	10000			
Freshwater	19.94			
Saltwater	970			
N+P Emissions kg/ FU	Nearshore	RAS		
Nitrogen	11100	777		
Phosphorus	1100	77		
Chemicals				
acetic	0.2522			
hydrogen peroxide	0.2522			
Bleach	3.465			
Sodium thiosulfate	105.21			
Packaging	kg			
Styrofoam	11666.67			
Polystyrene	1051.56			
PET foam	6667.00			
cardboard	120.00			
total weight (kg)	7838.56			
total weight (tonnes)	7.84			
Transport (to Milan)				
<i>Transport - PT Farm</i>	<i>distance</i>	<i>tonnes</i>	<i>tkm</i>	
Farm to processor	77	100	7700	
Processor to distributor	2283	108	246564	
Distributor to supermarket	75	108	8100	
		total tkm	262364	
<i>Transport - GR Farm</i>				
Farm to processor	66	100	6600	
Processor to distributor	1998	108	215784	
Distributor to supermarket	75	108	8100	
		total tkm	230484	
<i>Transport - TR Farm</i>				
Farm to processor	30	100	3000	
Processor to distributor	2337	108	252396	
Distributor to supermarket	75	108	1080	
		total tkm	256476	

4. Identification and matching of inventory processes

For each of the intermediary flows identified in step 2, we identify a cradle-to-gate life cycle inventory process from the Ecolnvent database – one of the two main life cycle databases, or from other compatible food specific data bases (e.g. agribalyse, agrifootprint, the world food database). These different processes are categorized in Table 2 for the sea bream example according to the different types of intermediary flows.

Table 3. Identified inventory processes from Ecolnvent database corresponding to the intermediary flows determined in step 2

Process #	Activity Name	Geography	Reference Product Name	Reference Product Unit	Reference Product Amount	Indicator	global warming potential kg CO2 Eq	human health min. lost	ecosystem quality species.yr	natural resources USD 2013	energy content MJ/eq	CO2 fossil kg	Check combination included gCO2/MJ
feed													
17683	market for sweet corn	GLO	sweet corn	kg	1	0.277	5.38E-01	4.0299E-09	0.02010826	2.58	0.198	76.5	
20840	wheat production	RoW	wheat grain	kg	1	0.665	1.18E+00	3.0328E-08	0.03468439	4.86	0.337	69.4	
20824	market for wheat flour	RoW	wheat flour	kg	1	0.869	1.53E+00	3.4131E-08	0.05288366	7.12	0.517	72.6	
15075	soybean meal to generic market for protein feed	GLO	protein feed, 100% crude	kg	1	2.744	2.11E+00	3.3252E-08	0.03682315	6.75	2.522	373.8	
7407	fish oil to generic market for energy feed	GLO	energy feed, gross	MJ	1	0.035	5.89E-02	2.0912E-10	0.0038291	0.49	0.031	69.1	
7909	fishmeal and fish oil production, 63-65% protein, from fish residues	RoW	fish oil, from anchovy	kg	1	2.929	3.44E+00	1.3815E-08	0.23237634	33.92	2.648	76.0	
15029	market for rape oil, crude	RoW	rape oil, crude	kg	1	1.689	3.48E+00	6.7002E-08	0.10433949	14.04	0.854	60.8	
7916	market for fish oil, from anchovy	GLO	fish oil, from anchovy	kg	1	1.340	2.27E+00	8.0719E-09	0.14780323	19.04	1.201	63.1	
7926	fishmeal and fish oil production, 63-65% protein, from fresh anchovy and fish residues	RoW	fishmeal, 63-65% protein	kg	1	1.396	1.86E+00	7.1349E-09	0.10336602	15.66	1.228	78.4	
7929	market for fishmeal, 63-65% protein	GLO	fishmeal, 63-65% protein	kg	1	1.243	2.02E+00	7.4192E-09	0.09362153	13.70	1.073	78.9	
19230	soybean oil, refined, to generic market for vegetable oil, refined	RoW	vegetable oil, refined	kg	1	7.128	6.08E+00	1.1227E-07	0.12323726	23.54	6.288	267.1	
infrastructure													
14650	market for polyethylene, low density, granulate	GLO	polyethylene, low density, granulate	kg	1	2.482	2.61E+00	1.0241E-08	0.65920119	82.78	2.056	24.8	
14704	market for polystyrene, general purpose	GLO	polystyrene, general purpose	kg	1	3.748	3.19E+00	1.4095E-08	0.75565114	90.59	2.814	31.1	
14544	market for nylon 6	GLO	nylon 6	kg	1	9.373	7.61E+00	3.1733E-08	0.92920081	125.90	5.608	44.5	
14671	market for polypropylene, granulate	GLO	polypropylene, granulate	kg	1	2.296	2.26E+00	9.2187E-09	0.67880072	82.23	1.876	22.8	
14725	market for polyurethane, flexible foam, flame retardant	GLO	polyurethane, flexible foam, flame retardant	kg	1	5.354	6.68E+00	2.3496E-08	0.74640801	106.52	4.215	39.6	
14733	polyvinylchloride production, bulk polymerisation	RoW	polyvinylchloride, bulk polymerised	kg	1	2.526	3.00E+00	1.0722E-08	0.44283076	59.28	2.177	36.7	
1699	cast iron production	RoW	cast iron	kg	1	1.772	1.06E+01	7.6174E-09	0.219786	20.99	1.581	74.4	
2147	chromium steel pipe production	GLO	chromium steel pipe	kg	1	5.341	2.51E+01	2.6396E-08	0.39500779	62.42	4.801	76.9	
2147	chromium steel pipe production	GLO	chromium steel pipe	kg	1	5.341	2.51E+01	2.6396E-08	0.39500779	62.42	4.801	76.9	
17287	market for steel, low-alloyed	GLO	steel, low-alloyed	kg	1	1.979	7.50E+00	8.917E-09	0.2295296	22.27	1.766	79.3	
2429	concrete block production	RoW	concrete block	kg	1	0.144	1.56E-01	6.2248E-10	0.00815022	1.13	0.135	118.9	
14671	market for polypropylene, granulate	GLO	polypropylene, granulate	kg	1	2.296	2.26E+00	9.2187E-09	0.67880072	82.23	1.876	22.8	
16151	market for selective coat, stainless steel sheet, black chrome	GLO	selective coat, stainless steel sheet, black chrome	m2	1	1.135	9.93E+00	9.4339E-09	0.0693721	15.80	1.013	60.1	
8271	market for glass fibre	GLO	glass fibre	kg	1	2.539	3.88E+00	1.2516E-08	0.20800067	36.50	2.202	60.3	
2196	market for clay	RoW	clay	kg	1	0.011	2.32E-02	6.4238E-11	0.0037185	0.14	0.010	68.9	
14732	market for polyvinylchloride, bulk polymerised	GLO	polyvinylchloride, bulk polymerised	kg	1	2.613	3.11E+00	1.1184E-08	0.45452281	60.57	2.256	37.2	
15733	market for sand	RoW	sand	kg	1	0.013	1.71E-02	9.5467E-11	0.00155239	0.19	0.012	69.0	
8804	market for heat pump, 30kW	GLO	heat pump, 30kW	unit	1	5043.944	1.21E+04	2.9663E-05	227.758174	25119.76	1573.032	62.6	
electricity													
7039	electricity, medium voltage, residual mix	PT	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.365	3.48E-01	1.63E-09	0.03526827	6.44	0.322	50.0	
6983	electricity, from municipal waste incineration to generic market for electricity, medium	DK	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.000	0.00E+00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000	ndW/01	
7037	electricity, medium voltage, residual mix	NO	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.486	4.34E-01	1.937E-09	0.03436419	9.63	0.442	46.0	
7019	electricity, medium voltage, residual mix	DK	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.628	5.68E-01	2.4941E-09	0.03792398	10.56	0.573	54.2	
6294	electricity production, photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si	PT	electricity, low voltage	kWh	1	0.063	1.17E-01	5.17E-10	0.00454322	0.84	0.055	65.7	
7116	market for electricity, medium voltage	GR	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.718	1.13E+00	3.7766E-09	0.04020198	11.12	0.669	60.1	
6295	electricity production, photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si	RoW	electricity, low voltage	kWh	1	0.080	1.48E-01	6.5404E-10	0.0057475	1.05	0.070	65.7	
6296	electricity production, photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si	NO	electricity, low voltage	kWh	1	0.065	1.20E-01	5.3347E-10	0.00487004	0.86	0.057	65.7	
7197	market for electricity, medium voltage	TR	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.587	2.14E+00	2.9767E-09	0.01973884	6.67	0.547	82.0	
7176	market for electricity, medium voltage	PT	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.335	3.69E-01	1.5161E-09	0.02846786	5.38	0.295	54.9	
7100	market for electricity, medium voltage	DK	electricity, medium voltage	kWh	1	0.211	2.37E-01	1.2893E-09	0.01045060	3.70	0.189	51.1	
4434	electricity production, wind, 1-3MW turbines, offshore	PT	electricity, high voltage	kWh	1	0.016	4.67E-02	8.2912E-11	0.00154771	0.20	0.014	72.2	
chemicals													
106	acetic acid production, product in 98% solution state	RoW	acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state	kg	1	2.487	3.14E+00	1.0689E-08	0.38073336	57.03	1.937	34.0	
9987	hydrogen peroxide production, product in 50% solution state	RoW	hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	kg	1	1.480	2.10E+00	6.1298E-09	0.13766152	21.98	1.242	56.5	
16955	market for sodium hypochlorite, without water, in 15% solution state	RoW	sodium hypochlorite, without water, in 15% solution state	kg	1	2.579	3.86E+00	1.1968E-08	0.20240795	34.35	2.289	66.6	
16925	market for sodium silicofluoride	GLO	sodium silicofluoride	kg	1	136.423	7.49E+02	1.3437E-06	15.627775	1914.09	120.022	62.7	
17760	market for tap water	RoW	tap water	kg	1	0.001	2.51E-03	5.4559E-12	7.9774E-05	0.02	0.001	68.1	
packaging													
14704	market for polystyrene, general purpose	GLO	polystyrene, general purpose	kg	1	3.748	3.19E+00	1.4095E-08	0.75565114	90.59	2.814	31.1	
14717	market for polyurethane, flexible foam	RoW	polyurethane, flexible foam	kg	1	5.380	6.80E+00	2.3278E-08	0.759516	106.93	4.184	39.1	
19801	market for waste paperboard	PT	waste paperboard	kg	-1	1.047	7.54E-01	3.7963E-09	0.00400729	0.51	0.028	54.8	
9415	heat, from municipal waste incineration to generic market for heat district or industrial	PT	heat, district or industrial, other than nd	MJ	-1	0.000	0.00E+00	0.00	0.00	0.000	ndW/01		
19801	market for waste paperboard	PT	electricity, for reuse in municipal waste	kg	-1	1.047	7.54E-01	3.7963E-09	0.00400729	0.51	0.028	54.8	
19912	market for waste plastic, mixture	PT	waste plastic, mixture	kg	-1	0.812	8.91E-01	2.5556E-09	0.00424447	0.49	0.749	152.8	
19836	market for waste paperboard, unsorted	without Swt	waste paperboard, unsorted	kg	-1	0.045	4.59E-02	2.0432E-10	0.00609211	0.64	0.041	63.8	
19794	market for waste paperboard	GR	waste paperboard	kg	-1	1.453	1.04E+00	5.3659E-09	0.00299419	0.41	0.019	46.8	
19804	market for waste paperboard	RoW	waste paperboard	kg	-1	1.996	1.63E+00	7.1914E-09	0.00107543	0.12	0.008	67.5	
19895	market for waste plastic, mixture	GR	waste plastic, mixture	kg	-1	0.154	6.41E-01	6.9278E-10	0.00259789	0.29	0.076	257.8	
19915	market for waste plastic, mixture	RoW	waste plastic, mixture	kg	-1	0.605	1.49E+00	2.1932E-09	0.00120076	0.14	0.485	3506.5	
transport													
18364	market for transport, freight, lorry with refrigeration machine, 7.5-16 ton, EURO3, cart	GLO	transport, freight, lorry with refrigeration machine ton*km	unit	1	0.287	3.08E-01	1.3765E-09	0.03925888	4.25	0.261	61.5	
3004	diesel, burned in fishing vessel	ES	diesel, burned in fishing vessel	MJ	1	0.094	2.48E-01	9.2303E-10	0.01267709	1.30	0.086	66.3	
14149	market for petrol, unleaded	RoW	petrol, unleaded	kg	1	0.959	1.08E+00	4.3776E-09	0.54933212	56.38	0.658	11.7	
outputs													
10266	market for inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	PT	inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	kg	1	5.793	7.02E+00	2.7368E-08	0.66871881	93.27	4.955	53.1	
10385	market for inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	PT	inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	kg	1	2.900	4.25E+00	1.6158E-08	0.31865888	45.00	2.549	56.6	
10243	market for inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	GR	inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	kg	1	5.819	8.97E+00	3.2425E-08	0.68816379	95.11	5.023	52.8	
10275	market for inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	TR	inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	kg	1	6.290	9.28E+00	3.1501E-08	0.57400512	87.43	5.160	59.0	
10362	market for inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	GR	inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	kg	1	3.399	5.59E+00	2.0467E-08	0.37744766	52.13	2.959	56.8	
10394	market for inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	TR	inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	kg	1	3.890	5.49E+00	1.9844E-08	0.33237943	45.42	3.069	67.6	
10239	market for inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	ES	inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	kg	1	5.152	5.99E+00	2.3592E-08	0.64422508	89.58	4.423	49.4	
10358	market for inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	ES	inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	kg	1	2.528	3.08E+00	1.2664E-08	0.27932825	39.15	2.220	56.7	
disposal													
9403	heat, from municipal waste incineration to generic market for heat district or industrial	ES	heat, district or industrial, other than nd	MJ	1	0.000	0.00E+00	0.00	0.00	0.000	ndW/01		
9417	heat, from municipal waste incineration to generic market for heat district or industrial	RoW	heat, district or industrial, other than nd	MJ	1	0.000	1.19E-03	2.6132E-12	2.3911E-05	0.00	0.000	71.4	
7904	market for fish freezing plant	GLO	fish freezing plant	unit	1	60.078	1.49E+02	8.132E-07	4.96174554	663.97	50.634	76.3	
7905	fish freezing, small fish	RoW	fish freezing, small fish	kg	1	0.443	5.62E-01	2.3774E-09	0.07484248	9.95	0.379	38.1	
7917	fish residues, Recycled Content cut-off	GLO	fish residues	kg	1	0.000	0.00E+00	0.00	0.00	0.000	ndW/01		

5. Inventory impact assessment

The intermediary flows from part 2 (Table 2) are linked to the overall list of identified LCA database processes from part 3 (Table 3) in the inventory and impact assessment spreadsheet (Figure 10) to determine the environmental impact assessment.

Scenario	Step	Process	Ecoinvent process	Region	Reference Product Name	Quantity/FU	Reference Product	Carbon Footprint CO ₂ -Eq/unit	Carbon footprint (kg CO ₂ /FU)	Percentage of carbon footprint
Offshore GR	Feed	7908	fishmeal and fish oil production, 63-65% protein, from fish residues	RoW	fish oil, from anchovy	40000	kg	2.93E+00	1.17E+05	17.37%
Offshore GR	Feed	7916	market for fish oil, from anchovy	GLO	fish oil, from anchovy	18000	kg	1.34E+00	2.41E+04	3.58%
Offshore GR	Feed	20840	wheat production	RoW	wheat grain	26000	kg	6.65E-01	1.73E+04	2.56%
Offshore GR	Feed	15075	soybean meal to generic market for protein feed	GLO	protein feed, 100% crude	42000	kg	2.74E+00	1.15E+05	17.09%
Offshore GR	Feed	20824	market for wheat flour	RoW	wheat flour	30000	kg	8.69E-01	2.61E+04	3.87%
Offshore GR	Feed	17683	market for sweet corn	GLO	sweet corn	22000	kg	2.77E-01	6.09E+03	0.90%
Offshore GR	Feed	15209	market for rape oil, crude	RoW	rape oil, crude	10000	kg	1.69E+00	1.69E+04	2.50%
Offshore GR	Feed	19230	soybean oil, refined, to generic market for vegetable oil, refined	GLO	vegetable oil, refined	8000	kg	7.13E+00	5.70E+04	8.46%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	14650	market for polyethylene, low density, granulate	GLO	polyethylene, low density, granulate	16664.6	kg	2.48E+00	4.14E+04	6.13%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	14704	market for polystyrene, general purpose	GLO	polystyrene, general purpose	0.02407	kg	3.75E+00	9.02E-02	0.00%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	13454	market for nylon 6	RoW	nylon 6	4121.4	kg	9.37E+00	3.86E+04	5.73%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	14671	market for polypropylene, granulate	GLO	polypropylene, granulate	4298.5399	kg	2.30E+00	9.87E+03	1.46%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	14725	market for polyurethane, flexible foam, flame retardant	GLO	polyurethane, flexible foam, flame retardant	0.05577	kg	5.35E+00	2.99E-01	0.00%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	14733	polyvinylchloride production, bulk polymerisation	RoW	polyvinylchloride, bulk polymerised	0.071	kg	2.53E+00	1.79E-01	0.00%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	1699	cast iron production	RoW	cast iron	0.0022	kg	1.77E+00	3.90E-03	0.00%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	2147	chromium steel pipe production	GLO	chromium steel pipe	0.0672	kg	5.34E+00	3.59E-01	0.00%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	2147	chromium steel pipe production	GLO	chromium steel pipe	801.92	kg	5.34E+00	4.28E+03	0.64%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	17287	market for steel, low-alloyed	GLO	steel, low-alloyed	5509.88	kg	1.98E+00	1.09E+04	1.62%
Offshore GR	Infrastructure	2429	concrete block production	RoW	concrete block	0.0384	kg	1.44E-01	5.51E-03	0.00%
Offshore GR	Production	7116	market for electricity, medium voltage	GR	electricity, medium voltage	814	kWh	7.18E-01	5.84E+02	0.09%
Offshore GR	Production	3004	diesel, burned in fishing vessel	GLO	diesel, burned in fishing vessel	1400	MJ	9.36E-02	1.31E+02	0.02%
Offshore GR	Production	14149	market for petrol, unleaded	RoW	petrol, unleaded	190	kg	9.59E-01	1.82E+02	0.03%
Offshore GR	Production	17760	market for tap water	RoW	tap water	19.94	kg	1.24E-03	2.47E-02	0.00%
Offshore GR	Production	10243	market for inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	GR	inorganic nitrogen fertiliser, as N	11100	kg	5.82E+00	6.46E+04	9.58%
Offshore GR	Production	10362	market for inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	GR	inorganic phosphorus fertiliser, as P2O5	1100	kg	3.40E+00	3.74E+03	0.55%
Offshore GR	Production	106	acetic acid production, product in 98% solution state	RoW	acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state	0.2522	kg	2.49E+00	6.27E-01	0.00%
Offshore GR	Production	9987	hydrogen peroxide production, product in 50% solution state	RoW	hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	0.2522	kg	1.48E+00	3.73E-01	0.00%
Offshore GR	Production	16855	market for sodium hypochlorite, without water, in 15% solution state	RoW	sodium hypochlorite, without water, in 15% solution state	3.465	kg	2.58E+00	8.94E+00	0.00%
Offshore GR	Production	16925	market for sodium silver thiosulfate	GLO	sodium silver thiosulfate	105.21	kg	1.36E+02	1.44E+04	2.13%
Offshore GR	Packaging	14704	market for polystyrene, general purpose	GLO	polystyrene, general purpose	1051.56	kg	3.75E+00	3.94E+03	0.58%
Offshore GR	Packaging	14717	market for polyurethane, flexible foam	RoW	polyurethane, flexible foam	6667	kg	5.38E+00	3.59E+04	5.32%
Offshore GR	Packaging	19836	market for waste paperboard, unsorted	Europe with	waste paperboard, unsorted	120	kg	4.48E-02	5.38E+00	0.00%
Offshore GR	Transport	18364	market for transport, freight, lorry with refrigeration machine, 7.5-11t	GLO	transport, freight, lorry with refrigeration machine, 7.5-11t	254334.3349	metric ton*k	2.87E-01	7.29E+04	10.81%
Offshore GR	Disposal	9415	heat, from municipal waste incineration to generic market for heat	PT	heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas		MJ	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00%
Offshore GR	Disposal	19784	market for waste paperboard	GR	waste paperboard	120	kg	-1.49E+00	-1.79E+02	-0.03%
Offshore GR	Disposal	19895	market for waste plastic, mixture	GR	waste plastic, mixture	1051.56	kg	-1.54E-01	-1.62E+02	-0.02%

Figure 11. Final calculation spreadsheet for inventory and impact assessment

Figure 12. The carbon footprint of the modeled farm scenarios in kilograms- CO₂ equivalent

Using the literature values from previous LCA studies on sea bream farming using recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) and nearshore farms, a carbon footprint was calculated using the inventory data. The two modeled farms were in Greece, where most sea bream farms are in the European Union. In comparison, a nearshore farm with electricity and transport from Turkey was modeled, and a Greece scenario used 100% photovoltaic energy. It is only with 100% photovoltaic that the carbon footprint of the RAS system becomes comparable with offshore production, while the RAS farm

connected to a Greek electricity grid shows the highest carbon footprint (Figure 11). This emphasizes the importance of relying on renewable electricity sources to have the RAS system being competitive, while reducing nitrogen and phosphate emissions and eutrophication impacts.

6. Conclusions

The present deliverable D6.2 aims to establish a data inventory supporting the FishEUTrust project's sustainability and impact assessment by detailing the collection and treatment of farm and supply chain data. By systematically gathering detailed data on production, feed, infrastructure, processing, distribution, and labor from aquaculture farms, the project establishes a robust inventory for evaluating environmental and socio-economic impacts. The methodology includes determining intermediary flows, creating correspondence tables for LCI processes, and performing detailed impact assessments.

Using LCA studies, the carbon footprint of RAS and nearshore sea bream farms in Greece and Turkey was modeled. Results show that RAS systems require renewable energy sources, such as 100% photovoltaic energy, to be competitive with offshore production while reducing emissions and eutrophication impacts.

Further D6.2 represents the sound basis for WP6 primary deliverable *D6.1: Roadmap for improvements and sustainable growth of aquaculture supply chain including standardization and policy*. Further steps in WP6 include creating evaluation reports every 6-months to provide a proper supervision and analysis of data collection process. For this, the partners' roles in the data quality reporting need to be identified to guarantee a smooth communication flow and the process of data collection reporting.

The comprehensive data collection and analysis methodology in WP6 will support robust sustainability and impact assessments within the FishEUTrust project, providing insights into optimizing aquaculture production for environmental and socio-economic benefits.

